

DIELECTRIC MONITORING OF THE CHEMORHEOLOGICAL BEHAVIOR OF EPOXY BASED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The final properties of thermoset matrix composites are strongly dependent on processing parameters such as viscosity and degree of reaction of the resin. Dielectric properties are sensitive to the chemical-physical changes occurring in reacting systems and can be related to these parameters. The evolution of the viscosity during autoclave processing is responsible for the resin flow and determines the conditions for pressure application. Therefore availability of an "in-situ" measurement of a structure sensitive parameter quantitatively related to degree of reaction and viscosity represents a big potential for on line cure monitoring. A commercial TGDDM-DDS based epoxy system is studied by calorimetric, rheological and dielectric analysis under isothermal and non-isothermal conditions. A correlation between the main cure parameters, the degree of reaction and viscosity, and the dielectric properties of the reactive system is proposed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dielectric sensors have been proposed in the last years as in-situ sensors capable to provide informations that can be correlated to the fundamental process variables during cure [1-3]. The dielectric behavior of thermosets during cure was deeply analyzed by Senturia and Sheppard [1]. However, intrinsic difficulties and unresolved issues related to the generation and interpretation of the results of dielectric measurements are still being discussed [3]. In order to apply dielectric measurements to process control dielectric sensors must be able to give in-situ and on-line reliable measurements of some dielectric property during cure. These properties must be correlated with the material properties (degree of reaction and viscosity) using fundamental or, at least, phenomenological models and finally such models must be implemented in control and optimization algorithms. Nowadays the use of dielectric properties to monitor material properties is mainly dependent on the availability of good correlations developed for different polymeric matrices. In this paper a commercial high temperature epoxy system for aeronautical applications is studied by calorimetric, rheological and dielectric analysis under isothermal and non-isothermal conditions. Then a relationship between a dielectric property (ionic resistivity) and the degree of reaction and viscosity during cure of an epoxy matrix for advanced composites is proposed.

2. ANALYSIS OF THE DIELECTRIC BEHAVIOR OF REACTING SYSTEMS

Considering the large variety of epoxy systems and their precursors, and the inevitable vicissitudes of the batch-to-batch characteristics and hygrothermal histories, it is clear that a

fundamental correlation between a dielectric property and a material variable would not be more useful than a calibration procedure for each batch. At present, however, such correlations either fundamental or phenomenological, are not available and data obtained in dielectric measurements have been correlated only qualitatively to the processing parameters (viscosity and degree of reaction) [2, 4]. Therefore, the development of phenomenological expressions accounting essentially for ripetibility, accuracy and easy calibration procedures is still needed. Research dealing with the correlation of dielectric constant and/or dielectric loss (ϵ' and ϵ'' respectively) with cure parameters has been devoted to the derivation of fundamental expressions which can then be used to describe the experimentally obtained results. Many difficulties arise from this approach since in polymeric systems the local internal electric field, responsible of the dielectric response of the material, is not known a priori. In fact its determination is difficult, as the number of dipoles per unit volume is not fixed, and the response of different dipoles to the electric field varies as a function of the size of the segment to which the dipole is attached and of the surroundings that hinder the dipole rotation to a different degree. Moreover a direct correlation of ϵ' (or ϵ'') with viscosity and degree of reaction has never been successfully attempted in literature.

On the other hand the ionic resistivity can be considered as the more interesting dielectric parameter for cure monitoring. Ionic resistivity is determined with the currently available sensor instruments assuming that free migrating ions are initially present, although in small amount, in the resin formulation. Free ions can be present as normal impurities, residues of precursor materials used in the synthesis of the polymer matrix or inorganic catalyzers for the crosslinking reaction.

Ionic conductivity (σ) is measured from dielectric loss, considering that the contribution of the dipole orientation to the dielectric loss response becomes negligible when:

$$(\epsilon_r - \epsilon_u)(\omega\tau)/(1 + \omega^2\tau^2) \ll \sigma/\omega\epsilon_0 \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_u is the "unrelaxed" complex permittivity given only by the contribution of atomic and electronic polarization and ϵ_r is the "relaxed" complex permittivity, obtained when the highest degree of dipole orientation is attained in the material at given temperature and electric field. Parameters τ and ω are relaxation time and angular frequency, respectively and ϵ_0 is the permittivity of the free space, equal to 8.854×10^{-12} Farads/m. When this inequality holds, Eq. 1 may be written as:

$$\epsilon'' = \sigma/\omega\epsilon_0 \quad (2)$$

Therefore, in this situation the ionic conductivity and the ionic resistivity (ρ) can be calculated from:

$$\sigma = 1/\rho = \omega\epsilon_0\epsilon'' \quad (3)$$

The effects of dipole orientation are frequency dependent and therefore the ionic resistivity can be evaluated at different frequencies during the polymerization applying Eq. 3 according with the procedures indicated elsewhere [5].

3. EXPERIMENTAL

The epoxy system analyzed was a commercial grade resin (Hercules 8552) produced by Hercules based on mixtures of *Tetra-Glicidyl Diamino Diphenyl Methane* (TGDDM) epoxy and *Diamino Diphenyl Sulfone* (DDS).

Dielectric analysis was performed under isothermal and non-isothermal conditions using a Micromet System II Dielectrometer. Data are collected between 10^{-1} e 10^5 Hz for each experiment. The thermocalorimetric characterization was carried out in isothermal and dynamic conditions in a Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) Mettler DSC 30. A Rheometrics dynamic visco-analyzer operating at 1-10 Hertz equipped with disposable parallel disks was used for the rheological characterization.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The advancement of the polymerization reaction is measured by DSC experiments defining the degree of reaction (α) as:

$$\alpha = 1/Q_T \int_0^t dQ/dt dt \quad (4)$$

where Q_T indicates the maximum amount of heat of reaction obtained during dynamic scans and dQ/dt is the heat flux measured from a baseline. The heat of reaction developed during an isothermal test (Q_{it}) is usually lower than Q_T indicating that the polymerization process can not be completed in this conditions. Then, a maximum degree of reaction achieved during isothermal tests can be calculated as $\alpha_m = Q_{it}/Q_T$ [6]. This is a consequence of the structural changes produced by the polymerization reactions which are associated with an increase of the glass transition temperature, T_g , of the reactive polymer. When the increasing T_g approaches the isothermal cure temperature the molecular mobility is strongly reduced and the reaction becomes diffusion controlled and eventually stops. The behavior of α_m as a function of the isothermal test temperature shows a linear dependence:

$$\alpha_m = a + b T \quad (5)$$

This behavior reminds the dependence between the glass transition temperature and the degree of reaction for a reactive polymer. In fact it is possible to assume that the value of the T_g reached by the polymeric matrix during the isothermal test is on the order of the value of the test temperature. It is clear that Eq. 5 holds for temperatures lower than the maximum glass transition temperature characteristic of the reacting system. The values of the parameters a and b , computed for the studied system, are given in Table 1.

The ionic resistivity of the resin depends on the mobility of ions, related with the network development which is a function of the advancement of the polymerization reaction, the most interesting variable for cure monitoring from the technological point of view. The evolution of resistivity must be modelled or following the path of a more fundamental analysis based on the knowledge of the number and type of ions present in the resin (with the technological limits above underlined) or an empirical relationship between resistivity (ρ) and degree of reaction (α) must be developed accounting also for the effects of temperature. The following simple expression is proposed for the isothermal cure:

$$\alpha = \alpha_m \frac{\log(\rho) - \log(\rho_0)}{\log(\rho_{max}) - \log(\rho_0)} \left[\frac{\log(\rho_{max})}{\log(\rho)} \right]^p \quad (6)$$

Where ρ_0 is the ionic resistivity of the unreacted resin, ρ_{max} is the maximum value reached at the end of an isothermal cure and p is a parameter temperature independent. In Fig. 1 degree of reaction curves obtained from calorimetric analysis are well compared with resistivity data processed according with Eq. 6, at four different temperatures. An average value of $p = 1.75$ was obtained by regression analysis for the temperature range analyzed. It should be noted that α_m must be included in Eq. 6 in order to take into account the incomplete polymerization reaction characteristic of the isothermal experiments.

In order to calculate the degree of reaction also in non-isothermal conditions, the temperature dependence of ρ_0 and of ρ_{max} . The ionic resistivity of the unreacted resin (ρ_0) is modelled with the classic William Landel and Ferry (WLF) equation [1]:

$$\rho = \rho_{g0} \exp \frac{C_1(T - T_g(\alpha))}{C_2 + T - T_g(\alpha)} \quad (7)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are constants, and ρ_{g0} is the pre-exponential constant representing the resistivity of the unreacted resin at the glass transition temperature T_{g0} . Figure 2 shows the

good correspondence between a WLF expression and the experimental data obtained at constant heating rate. The parameters of Eq. 7 obtained by non-linear regression are listed in Table 1. A more complex situation for ρ_{\max} must be considered. Since in isothermal experiments the reaction end is mainly determined by vitrification, the maximum resistivity measured for a glassy system is a complex function of the final degree of reaction, α_m , and of the temperature. On the other hand, in dynamic experiments the actual temperature is always higher than the glass transition of the sample and the maximum resistivity measured at the end of the polymerization corresponds to a temperature higher than the maximum glass transition of the cured resin ($T_{g\infty}$). In fact the values of ρ_{\max} obtained in isothermal conditions correspond to lower mobility conditions and are one order of magnitude higher than those obtained at temperatures higher than $T_{g\infty}$. This behavior is shown in Fig. 3 where the resistivity of glassy samples obtained at the end of isothermal curing experiments, and of rubbery samples measured at temperatures higher than $T_{g\infty}$, are represented. A drop in the resistivity values is observed in correspondence of the glass transition temperature while the linear behavior of the logarithm of the resistivity as a function of $1/T$ indicates that the temperature dependence of ρ_{\max} can be well represented by an Arrhenius equation:

$$\rho_{\max} = K \exp(E/RT) \quad (8)$$

The parameters of Eq. 8 are given in Table 1 for each of the two temperature ranges. Calorimetric results and predictions of the complete model (Eqs. 5-8) obtained in a simulation of a typical autoclave cycle are shown in Fig. 4. The same value of the parameter p in Eq. 11 ($p=1.75$) is used for isothermal and non-isothermal conditions. The proposed model provides good predictions of degree of reaction values in different thermal conditions. In order to calculate the viscosity of the commercial epoxy system studied in this work as a function of temperature and degree of reaction, the developed expressions are combined with the model presented by Kenny and Opalicki [7]:

$$\eta = \eta_{g0} \exp \frac{C_{1\eta}(T-T_g(\alpha))}{C_{2\eta}+T-T_g(\alpha)} [\alpha_g/(\alpha_g-\alpha)]^n \quad (9)$$

where η is the viscosity, η_{g0} is the viscosity of the unreacted resin at its glass transition temperature, α_g is the extent of reaction at the gel point and $C_{1\eta}$, $C_{2\eta}$ and n are constants to be determined by regression analysis of the experimental data. The dependence of T_g from the degree of reaction is well represented by a linear relationship:

$$T_g = q + s \alpha \quad (10)$$

The parameters of the rheological model given by Eqs. 14 and 15, as reported by Kenny and Opalicki [7] are summarized in Table 1. Degree of reaction values obtained applying the complete model (Eqs. 5-8) can be used in the chemorheological model (Eq. 9 and 10) for viscosity calculation. The comparison between experimental data and model results is very satisfactory for isothermal (Fig. 11) and non isothermal conditions (Fig. 12).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The experimental results obtained by thermal, dielectric and rheological measurements have been used for the development of a relationship between the ionic resistivity and the degree of reaction during the cure process of an epoxy matrix for advanced composites. Accounting also for the temperature dependence of the initial and final values of the resistivity, isothermal and non-isothermal degree of reaction data have been well represented by the proposed model. Finally, degree of reaction data calculated from dielectric measurements have been used in a chemorheological model for viscosity calculation, obtaining very good correspondence between measured and predicted values in isothermal and non-isothermal conditions. The proposed correlation between resistivity and degree of reaction can be considered a powerful tool for the determination of the end of the cure and for the monitoring of the viscosity evolution up to the gel point.

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6. REFERENCES

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Table 1. Parameters of Eqs. 5-10.

$T_{g0} = 267 \text{ K}$	$T_g = 500 \text{ K}$	$Ka = -2.211$	$b = 0.006715 \text{ K}^{-1}$	$p = 1.75$
$C_1 = 25.1$	$C_2 = 37.4 \text{ K}$		$\rho_{g0} = 7 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ ohm cm}$	
-				
$\ln(k) = 1.372 \text{ ohm cm}$	$E/R = 11076 \text{ K}^{-1}$, for $T < T_{g\infty}$			
$\ln(k) = -31.43 \text{ ohm cm}$	$E/R = 26959 \text{ K}^{-1}$, for $T < T_{g\infty}$			
-				
$C_{1\eta} = 32.7$	$C_{2\eta} = 37.4 \text{ K}$	$\eta_{g0} = 10^{12} \text{ Pa s}$		
$n = 1.91$	$\alpha_g = 0.271$	$q = 267 \text{ K}$	$s = 232 \text{ K}$	

Figure 1. Degree of reaction obtained in isothermal cure by DSC and by application of the proposed model to ionic resistivity data

Figure 2. WLF behaviour of the resistivity of unreacted resin

Figure 3. Resistivity as function of temperature for cured resin below and above $T_{g^{\infty}}$

Figure 4. Comparison between degree of reaction obtained in an autoclave cycle simulation (ramp 5 °C/min) by DSC and calculated using ionic resistivity data

Figure 5. Comparison between viscosity values obtained by the proposed model and experimental data in isothermal conditions

Figure 6. Comparison between viscosity values obtained by the proposed model and experimental data in an autoclave cycle simulation (ramp 5 °C/min)